

Spectrum of MRI Findings in Ankle Ligament InjuriesUrvija Shah¹, Arpit Kothari², Viplav Gandhi³¹Smt NHL Medical College²MD Radiology, Department of Radiology, Smt NHL Medical College³Professor and Head, Department of Radiology, Shardaben General Hospital

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Urvija Shah

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Ankle trauma is commonly encountered and is most often a sprain injury affecting the ligaments. Accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment rest on knowledge of complex ligamentous anatomy of ankle and the entire spectrum of pathologies. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is the imaging modality of choice for diagnosing ligament pathologies because of its multiplanar capability and high soft tissue contrast. In this article emphasis is given to the intricate and unique anatomy and orientation of ankle ligaments. Tears of ankle ligaments have been elaborated.

Materials and Methods: In a retrospective observational study, patient's data was collected from tertiary care unit from period of January 2024 to June 2024. Ankle MRI was performed using standard protocol on 100 cases.

Results: In this study, 50 percent cases had injury to lateral ligament complex of which 35 percent were anterior talofibular ligament, 5 percent were posterior talofibular ligament and 10 percent were calcaneofibular ligament. It concluded that lateral ligament complex tears are more common than medial ligament complex.

Conclusion: MRI visualizes ligamentous anatomy and pathology at the ankle and is being used with increasing frequency in patients following ankle sprains. MR images of ankle ligaments from a sample of patients with ankle pain or injury are presented and reviewed.

Keywords: Ankle Injury, Talofibular, Lateral Ligament Complex.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Ankle sprains are common injuries with a significant risk factor of development of chronic pain and ankle instability. MRI has been used as an effective modality to diagnose ligament tears and differentiate it from other causes of ankle pain like fracture and tendon injuries because of its superior soft tissue resolution. The lateral ligamentous complex is involved in the majority of ankle sprain injuries and comprises the anterior talofibular ligament (ATFL), the calcaneofibular ligament (CFL), and the posterior talofibular ligament (PTFL). Other ligaments involved are syndesmosis, spring ligament, medial ligament complex and deltoid ligament. An MRI scan of acutely injured ankle ligaments may demonstrate the presence of haemorrhage in the joint space and soft-tissue swelling over the lateral malleolus as well as high bone signal at ligament avulsion sites, which may be absent in patients with recurrent or chronic problems.[1]

The primary objective of this study is to evaluate accuracy of MRI in diagnosing ankle ligament injuries.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Patient's data was collected retrospectively from tertiary care unit from period of January 2024 to June 2024. The inclusion criteria 1) History of acute pain from injury. 2) Persistent swelling despite been on conservative analgesics and crepe bandages after 6 weeks.

Exclusion criteria included 1) Previous ankle surgeries. 2) Previously diagnosed tears from current presentation.

Patients scanned within interval of 3 months or less from time of injury whereas acute injury categorised and those scanned at an interval of more than 3 months whereas chronic injury categorised.

A sample of convenience was used.

MRI Ankle Protocol**Scan geometry [3]**

- in-plane spatial resolution: $\leq 0.3 \times 0.3$ mm
- field of view (FOV): 100-160 mm
- slice thickness: ≤ 3 mm

Planning [3]

Table 1: [3]

	Axial images	Coronal images	Sagittal images	axial oblique images
Angulation	perpendicular to the distal tibia and parallel to the tibiotalar joint	parallel to the malleolar axis	perpendicular to the malleolar axis	with a posteroinferior tilt of about 45° perpendicular to the posterior facet of the calcaneus
Volume	3-5 cm above the tibiotalar joint to the plantar fascia	include at least the whole tibiotalar joint, the talus and navicular bone	includes medial and lateral malleolus	include the tibiotalar joint and both malleoli

Discussion

Normal Appearance of Ligaments: The lateral ligament complex is most commonly injured of all ankle ligaments. It comprises of anterior talofibular, posterior talofibular and calcaneofibular ligaments imaged with routine axial and coronal PDFS and T2W images.

Figure 1: Anterior talofibular ligament being weakest of lateral ligaments most commonly injured. It is well visualized on fluid-sensitive sequences such as this axial T2-weighted image, of uniform thickness and low T1 and T2 signal intensity (arrow).[2]

Figure 2: Calcaneofibular ligament lies deep in relation to peroneal tendons and extends from lateral malleolar tip to trochlear eminence. Calcaneofibular is often partially imaged in coronal or axial planes.

Oblique axial proton density–weighted image of intact calcaneofibular ligament (arrow) shows regular contour and homogeneously low signal. [2]

Figure 3: Posterior talofibular is least frequently injured of three lateral ligaments. It extends from posterior talus (lateral tubercle) to fibular malleolar fossa. Posterior talofibular often appears striated on MRI because of its fibro-fatty composition. Normal posterior talofibular ligament (arrow) has linear striations on this axial proton density–weighted image. [2]

Medial ligament complex includes anterior tibiotalar, posterior tibiotalar ligaments. Medial ligament complex injuries are infrequent and commonly associated with malleolar fractures or other ligament injuries. Superficial ligaments have variable attachments and cross two joints. The deep

ligaments have talar attachments and cross one joint.

The three components that are visualized on MRI are tibiospring and tibionavicular ligaments in superficial layer and posterior tibiotalar ligament in deep layer. [2]

Figure 4: Tibiospring ligament connects medial malleolar colliculus to superomedial spring ligament. Coronal proton density–weighted image of intact tibiospring ligament shows its attachment to spring ligament (arrow). [2]

Figure 5: Tibionavicular ligament inserts onto navicular and is visible on only 55% of MR images of asymptomatic subjects. Because of its variable visualization, it is unreliable in assessing ligament injury. Coronal T2-weighted image shows intact tibionavicular ligament (arrow). [2]

Figure 6: Posterior tibiotalar is thickest of medial ligaments with intervening fat separating its fascicles, often resulting in striated appearance in normal ligament. Fascicular disruption, irregularity, and loss of striation are indicators of injury. Coronal T2-weighted image of intact posterior tibiotalar ligament shows continuous fibres and intervening fat between fascicles (arrow). [2]

Figure 7: Anterior tibiotalar ligament is thin and of uniformly low signal intensity on proton density-weighted images. Coronal proton density-weighted shows intact anterior tibiotalar ligament (arrow). [2]

Syndesmosis

Figure 8: Anterior inferior tibiofibular ligament extends from anterior tibial tubercle to fibular tubercle and is best visualized on axial images. Intact anterior inferior tibiofibular ligament is low in signal intensity on axial proton density-weighted image (arrow). [2]

Figure 9: Posterior inferior tibiofibular ligament extends from posterior tibial tubercle to posterior fibula. It (arrow) is seen on axial proton density-weighted image. [2]

Figure 10: Medioplantar oblique calcaneonavicular ligament extends from medial portion of navicular bone to calcaneal coronoid fossa and is best visualized in axial plane. Normal striated appearance of uninjured medioplantar oblique calcaneonavicular ligament is shown on axial T2-weighted image (arrow). [2]

Figure 11: Superomedial calcaneonavicular ligament originates from sustentaculum tali of calcaneus and inserts onto superomedial tarsal navicular.

It lies deep in relation to posterior tibial tendon (PTT). Superficial surface of superomedial calcaneonavicular ligament is composed of fibrocartilaginous gliding zone. Of three components of spring ligament complex, superomedial calcaneonavicular ligament is most likely to be injured. Coronal T2-weighted image

shows intact superomedial calcaneonavicular ligament (straight arrow) and adjacent PTT (curved arrow).

Normal tibiospring ligament is also visible (arrowhead). Asterisk indicates fibrocartilaginous gliding zone. [2]

Figure 12: Inferoplantar calcaneonavicular ligament lies anterior to medioplantar oblique calcaneonavicular ligament, extending from inferior navicular bone to calcaneal coronoid fossa. It is usually thickest of three components of spring ligaments and is seen in 91% of asymptomatic subjects

[13]. Sagittal T1-weighted image shows intact inferoplantar longitudinal calcaneonavicular ligament (arrow).[2]

Figure 13: Types of tear

Case Discussion

Case 1: A 25-year female presented with complaint of left ankle pain following sprain by inversion mechanism since 2 days.

Figure 14: Abnormal hyperintensity is noted involving posterior tibiofibular ligament on PDFS axial images; Indicates interstitial tear.

Case 2: A 35-year male presented with ankle pain after a week of road traffic accident.

Figure 15 Coronal PDFS images show abnormal hyperintensity within substance of calcaneofibular ligament (A) and posterior talofibular ligament (B), suggestive of interstitial tear.

Case 3: A 22-year football player presented with left ankle pain following injury by eversion mechanism.

Figure 16: Abnormal hyperintensity with partial discontinuity of fibres is noted involving spring ligament, indicates Partial thickness tear

Result and Analysis

In our retrospective observational study, out of 100 cases, 35 cases were of anterior talofibular ligament tear, 10 cases were of posterior talofibular ligament tear, 5 cases of calcaneofibular ligament tear, 40 cases were of spring ligament tear and 10 cases

were of deltoid ligament tear. Out of all cases assessed lateral ligament complex tear (ATFL, PTFL and calcaneofibular ligament) turned out to be commonest ligament involved in traumatic setup.

Table 2: Prevalance of MRI Findings among 100 Cases

MRI Findings	ATFL [35]	PTFL [5]	Calcaneonavicular ligament[10]	Spring ligament [40]	Deltoid ligament [10]
Abnormal hyper intensity	14	1	4	30	5
Discontinuity of fibres	21	4	6	10	5

Figure 17:**Conclusion**

Knowledge of anatomy and imaging appearance of normal and abnormal ankle ligaments on MRI with an understanding of biomechanics of injury aids in achieving accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment of ankle sprains. Depending on the MRI features and the clinical correlates (Drawers test, inversion and eversion tests), it is possible for the clinicians to grade the ankle injury from mild to severe and also assess instability. [4]

References

1. Accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging in diagnosing lateral ankle ligament injuries: A comparative study with surgical findings and timings of scans. Desmond Wei Tan, Daniel Jing Wen Teh, and Yu Han Chee
2. Ankle Ligaments on MRI: Appearance of Normal and Injured Ligaments, Authors: Kiley D. Perrich, Douglas W. Goodwin, Paul J. Hecht, and Yvonne Cheung Volume 193, Issue 3 <https://doi.org/10.2214/AJR.08.2286>
3. Feger J, Murphy A, Haouimi A, et al. Ankle protocol (MRI). Reference article, Radiopaedia.org (Accessed on 19 Jul 2024) <https://doi.org/10.53347/rID-80420>
4. Magnetic resonance imaging of ankle ligaments: A pictorial essay Yogini Nilkantha Sawant and Darshana Sanghvi
5. MR Imaging of the Ankle and Foot, Zehava S. Rosenberg, Javier Beltran, Jenny T. Bencardino 2000 https://doi.org/10.1148/radiographics.20.suppl_1.g00oc26s153